

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MUCCOADHESIVE BUCCAL PATCHES OF
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ABSTRACT

Dimenhydrinate is a H1 Antagonist; it is used in the treatment of vomiting caused by motion sickness. These controlled release Mucoadhesive buccal patches mainly prepared for release of the drug for longer period of time i.e., 10 hours and utilizing the drug to full extent avoiding unnecessary frequency of dosing. For the formulation of Mucoadhesive buccal patches HPMC E15, HEC, PVA and PVP were used as matrix forming agents. Other excipients used are Propylene glycol as a plasticizer. Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy confirmed the absence of any drug/polymers/excipients interactions. The Mucoadhesive buccal patches were prepared by solvent casting method using magnetic stirrer. The prepared controlled release Mucoadhesive buccal patches were evaluated for thickness, folding endurance, weight variation, water uptake, bioadhesive strength, drug content uniformity, surface pH, Mechanical strength, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), In-vitro release study, In vitro residence time, Ex-vivo drug release study, Stability study and Kinetic study. Formulation F3 showed good Bioadhesive strength and a controlled drug release and also shown good result for all other parameters when compared with all other formulations. Hence formulation F3 is considered to be the optimized formulation. Stability studies were carried out for F3 formulation they had showed good stability when stored at accelerated stability state as per the ICH guideline and the values were within a permissible limits. It was observed that Formulations F3 retained the drug release up to 24 hrs. All formulations were subjected for four different models viz. Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas model equations and all the formulations best fit in to the Peppas model by giving the values of diffusional exponent (n) in the range of 0.6-0.9 that indicate the formulation had release the drug by diffusion followed by erosion mechanism. It was revealed that polymer ratios had significant influence on drug release. Thus conclusion can be made that stable dosage form can be developed for Dimenhydrinate for controlled release by buccal patches.

KEYWORDS: Formulation, Evaluation, Mucoadhesive Buccal Patches, Dimenhydrinate.**INTRODUCTION**

The oral route of drug administration is the most common and preferred route for drug delivery, as it enables easy ingestion, self-medication, accurate dosage, flexible and controlled dosing schedule, and patient

compliance with a low chance of administration difficulty.^[1,2] It also has some major disadvantages such as the first-pass effect, gastrointestinal enzymatic degradation, and slow onset of action.^[3] To overcome these disadvantages, mucoadhesive drug delivery and

sublingual drug delivery could be better alternatives.^[4]

Mucoadhesive dosage forms are specially designed to adhere to the mucosal surface, thus intensifying retention of the drug at the site of application, while providing a controlled rate of drug release for better therapeutic outcome.^[5] To mention, a few mucoadhesive drug delivery systems are adhesive patches, adhesive gels, adhesive tablets, adhesive films, adhesive discs, etc.^[6] Several regions such as the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, the urogenital tract, the ear, the nasal route, and the airways in the body are lined by the mucosal layer. These are either single-layered epithelium found in the GI tract, bronchi, and intestines or multilayered stratified epithelium found in the esophagus, vagina, and cornea and are the potential sites where mucoadhesive drug delivery systems can be useful.^[6, 7]

Buccal mucosa is one of such mucosal site which has a high extent of vascularization and enables direct drain of blood flow into the jugular vein, which helps to avoid the possible metabolism of drugs by the gastrointestinal route and liver.^[8] The buccal delivery thus implies the absorption of medication through the mucosal lining of the buccal cavity. Easier drug administration, the possibility of prompt termination in the condition of unpredicted side effects and emergencies, the possibility of incorporating enzyme inhibitor/permeation enhancer, etc. are other major advantages of this drug delivery system.^[9, 10]

Various mucoadhesive polymers (natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic) used in this delivery system

become adhesive on hydration^[11], therefore can be used for targeting a drug to a particular region of the body. Initially, when the mucoadhesive product is in contact with the mucosal membrane, it swells and spreads, initializing deep contact with the mucosal layer and then mucoadhesive materials (polymers) are activated by the presence of moisture and drug releases slowly.^[12]

Dimenhydrinate is a member of drug belonging to the class of H₁ anti histamine used in treatment of post operative vomiting. Dimenhydrinate undergoes first pass metabolism in the liver and as a consequence the availability of Dimenhydrinate in general circulation is low and variable. Physicochemical properties of Dimenhydrinate like small dose lipophilicity, stability at buccal P^H, tasteless odorless and more absorption through buccal mucosa makes it an ideal candidate for administration by buccal route.

Hence in the present work an attempt is being made to formulate a buccal mucoadhesive dosage form for Dimenhydrinate in the form of buccal patches by using four different polymers Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC), Hydroxy Ethyl Cellulose (HEC), Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA), Poly Vinyl Pyrrolidone (PVP) to overcome the Hepatic metabolism and low bioavailability.

METHODOLOGY

The following materials & instruments were used for the preparation of Dimenhydrinate buccal patches.

Table No. 1: LIST OF CHEMICALS USED.

S.no	Name	Grade	supplier
1	Dimenhydrinate	Pharma	Aurabindo pharmaceuticals.
2	HPMC E15	USP/EP	Alkem laboratories
3	Hydroxy ethylcellulose	Laboratory	SD Fine ChemicalsLtd. Mumbai.
4	Poly vinyl alcohol	Laboratory	SD Fine ChemicalsLtd. Mumbai.
5	Poly vinylpyrrolidone	Laboratory	SD Fine ChemicalsLtd. Mumbai.
6	Propylene glycol	Laboratory	SD Fine ChemicalsLtd. Mumbai.
7	Potassiumdihydrogen phosphate	Laboratory	SD Fine ChemicalsLtd. Mumbai.
8	Disodium hydrogenphosphate	Laboratory	SD Fine ChemicalsLtd. Mumbai.

PREPARATION OF BUCCAL PATCHES

Patches containing Dimenhydrinate and HPMC E15, HEC, PVP, PVA different proportions was prepared by the solvent casting method. The drug was dissolved in 5ml of methanol and the polymers were dissolved in separate container with 20ml of distilled water under continuous stirring for 4 hours. After stirring, mix the drug and polymer solution. Propylene glycol was added into the solution as a plasticizer under constant stirring. The viscous solution was left over night to ensure a clear, bubble free solution. The solution was poured into a glass petridish and allowed to dry at 40⁰c temperature till a flexible patch was formed. Dried patch was removed carefully, checked any imperfections or air bubbles and cut into pieces of

1mm² area. The patches were packed in aluminum foil and stored in desiccators to maintain the integrity and elasticity of the patches. Table no.2 shows the composition of different buccal patches.

Table No. 2: composition of buccal patches of Dimenhydrinate.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Dimenhydrinate	250 mg									
HPMC E15	750 mg	----	250 mg	375 mg	500 mg	750 mg	----	250 mg	375 mg	500 mg
HEC	----	750 mg	500 mg	375 mg	250 mg	----	750 mg	500 mg	375 mg	250 mg
PVP	125 mg	----	----	----	----	----				
PVA	----	----	----	----	----	125 mg				
ETHANOL	5ml									
Propylene glycol	0.7 ml									
Distilled water	25ml									

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PREFORMULATION PARAMETERS

Determination of λ max of Dimenhydrinate

On the basis of preliminary identification test it was concluded that the drug complied the preliminary identification. From the scanning of drug, it was concluded that the drug had λ_{max} of 276 nm, which was equal to 276 nm as reported. Also, an IR spectrum was concordant with the reference spectrum of Dimenhydrinate.

Preparation of standard calibration curve of Dimenhydrinate.

From the standard curve of Dimenhydrinate, it was observed that the drug obeys Beer's law in concentration range of 1-10 μ g/ml in Distilled water. The linear Regression equation generated was used for the calculation of amount of drug.

Determination of IR spectrum of Dimenhydrinate.

Physical mixture of drug and polymer was characterized by FT-IR spectral analysis for any physical as well as chemical alteration of the drug characteristics. From the results, it was concluded that there was no interference in the functional group as the principle peaks of the Dimenhydrinate were found to be unaltered in the drug-polymer physical mixture, indicating they were compatible chemically.

Drug excipient compatibility studies

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies form an important part of Preformulation studies for the determination of interaction between drug and excipient. It is determined after storage of specific time period by using suitable analytical techniques and the results are indicating that there is no interaction between drug and excipients.

FORMULATION DESIGN

Formulation of the controlled release mucoadhesive buccal patches of Dimenhydrinate.

Total 10 formulations of Mucoadhesive buccal patches were prepared with different polymers such as HPMC E15, HEC, PVA and PVP in different Ratios and proportions by Solvent casting technique. The prepared Mucoadhesive patches were then evaluated for various physico-chemical tests like thickness, folding endurance, weight variation, water uptake, bioadhesive strength, drug content uniformity, surface p^H , Mechanical strength, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), In-vitro release study, In vitro residence time, Ex-vivo drug release study, Stability study and Kinetic study.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Physical properties

Thickness of patch

The thickness of the prepared buccal patches of each formulation was determined with in the range of 0.23-0.26mm.

Folding endurance:

The folding endurance of each formulation was determined with in the range of 302 to 318. It revealed that good flexibility of patch.

Mechanical strength

The values were found to be in the range of 5.28 to 12.94kg/mm². The values revealed that the patches were having good mechanical strength.

Water uptake study

Water uptake of all buccal patches containing Dimenhydrinate is given in table. The swelling of patch was changes with respect to polymer ratios. The values were found to be with in the range of 1.93 to 2.93.it was maximum for F3 i.e. 2.93. It is revealed that swelling nature of polymer.

Performance parameters

Content uniformity of active ingredient

Table shows the result of drug content uniformity in each formulation. Three replicates of each test were

carried out. The mean drug content was found to be in the range of 3.68 to 3.8 for (each patch size 10mm diameter) the prepared buccal patch formulations. It is indicating the uniform distribution of drug in polymer matrix.

Measurement of bioadhesive strength

An effective buccal mucosal device must maintain an intimate contact with mucus layer overlying the epithelial tissue. This parameter very important to successful utilization of these dosage forms. Hence in-vitro evaluation of buccal patches was carried out using porcine gastric mucosa. This gives the indirect measurement of bioadhesive strength in grams.

The maximum bioadhesive strength and force of adhesion was recorded for the formulation F3 and the values were 187.67 and 1.82 respectively.

The In-vitro residence time was recorded and the values were changing with different ratios of polymers and the maximum for F3 about 490 mins.

Measurement of surface P^H

They were found to be within the range of 6.3 to 6.6 for all formulations and were almost within the range of salivary p^H i.e. 6.2 to 7.4. There was no considerable difference in surface p^H of patches. It represents the better patient acceptability.

In vitro release study

The in-vitro dissolution was studied in phosphate buffer p^H 6.8. The In-vitro dissolution studies were carried out in triplicate and the results shown in the tables are mean of the replicate values. The In-vitro released data obtained for patches F1 to F10 are tabulated in table. The maximum release was observed in F3 formulation, it was up to 10 hours. The release is due to the uniform and proper mixing of drug and polymers which enables the drug to release in steady state manner.

Criteria for optimization

The formulation F3 is optimized on the basis of In-vitro

drug release, swelling index, long In-vitro residence time and good bioadhesive strength. The Ex-vivo release studies were performed by using 7.4 P^H saline phosphate buffer for formulation F3 by using porcine buccal mucosa as a model membrane and it was shown that good drug permeability across the membrane above 10 hours.

Stability study

Stability studies of the prepared buccal patches were carried out, by storing formulations F3 at, room temperature and humidity and 40^o C ± 2^o C / 75% RH ± 5% RH in humidity control oven for ninety days. Stability studies were carried out to predict the degradation that may occur over prolonged periods of storage at various temperatures and humidity for formulations F3 over a period of 90 days. The results of the stability studies, which were conducted for 90 days, are shown in table. The result obtained showed a slight decrease in, in vitro release of formulations F3 as compared to the fresh formulations F3. The shelf life of the fabricated device was calculated based on these parameters.

Kinetic study

To study the drug release kinetics, data obtained from In-Vitro drug release studies are plotted in various kinetic models. The curve fitting results of the release rate profile of the designed formulations gave an idea on the mechanism of drug release.

Based on the “n” values are ranging from 0.745-0.893 for all the formulations, the drug release was found to follow Anomalous (non-Fickian) diffusion. This value indicates a coupling of the diffusion and erosion mechanism (Anomalous diffusion) and indicates that the drug release was controlled by more than one process. Also, the drug release mechanism was best explained by zero order, as the plots showed the highest linearity (r² = 0.971), as the drug release was best fitted in zero order kinetics, it indicated that the rate of drug release is concentration independent.

Table No. 3: Interpretation of IR spectra.

S.no	Functional group	IR range	Assessment of peak (cm ⁻¹)
1	C-H Stretching in CH ₃ group	1020-1220	1041.60
2	C-H Stretching in aromatic ring	3100-3000	3030.27
3	N-H Stretching in Hetero aromatic ring	3500-3220	3329.25
4	C-Cl Stretching of mono chlorinated aromatic compound	750-700	702.11
5	C-H Stretching in Methoxy group	2815-2850	2818.09

Table No. 4: Evaluation of Physical parameters of different mucoadhesive buccal patches of Dimenhydrinate.

Formulation code	Physical parameters			
	Thickness (mm) ±S.D (n=3)	Folding endurance ±S.D (n=3)	Mechanical strength ±S.D (n=3) (kg/mm ²)	Water uptake ±S.D (n=3)
F1	0.23± 0.005	305± 4.04	5.28± 0.076	2.15± 0.64
F2	0.22± 0.014	305± 4.72	6.04± 0.056	2.02± 0.52
F3	0.24± 0.002	313± 2.51	12.94± 0.098	2.93± 0.102
F4	0.26± 0.0023	318± 2.51	12.64± 0.124	2.53± 0.23
F5	0.25± 0.001	302± 1.00	10.86± 0.132	1.95± 0.051
F6	0.23± 0.003	312± 2.51	6.84± 0.079	1.93± 0.153
F7	0.24± 0.023	318± 2.52	7.23± 0.32	2.07± 0.354
F8	0.26± 0.01	310± 5.50	9.45± 0.054	2.18± 0.243
F9	0.26± 0.034	309± 5.51	12.14± 0.045	2.46± 0.109

Table No 5: Evaluation of Performance parameters of different mucoadhesive buccal patches of Dimenhydrinate.

Formulation code	Performance parameters(Bio adhesive)		
	Bioadhesive strength(gms) ±S.D (n=3)	Force of adhesion(N) ±S.D(n=3)	Bond strength ±S.D (n=3) (kg/mm ²)
F1	144.3± 2.64	1.40± 0.03	453.02± 5.34
F2	149.34± 2.13	1.44± 0.02	432.12± 3.65
F3	187.67± 0.78	1.82± 0.05	586.09± 5.23
F4	176.28± 0.98	1.62± 0.01	543.63± 1.86
F5	167.33± 1.34	1.75± 0.01	513.78± 4.33
F6	132.64± 3.67	1.62± 0.06	421.12± 6.98
F7	134.23± 2.87	1.42± 0.04	435.47± 5.32
F8	167.35± 1.74	1.47± 0.03	564.65± 6.90
F9	168.23± 1.53	1.76± 0.01	523.34± 3.23
F10	159.46± 1.13	1.12± 0.01	498.21± 4.98

Table No. 6: Evaluation of Performance parameters of different mucoadhesive buccal patches of Dimenhydrinate.

Formulation code	Performance parameters(Bio adhesive)		
	Drug content(mgs) ±S.D (n=3)	Surface P ^H ±S.D(n=3)	Invitro residencetime (min)±S.D (n=3) (kg/mm ²)
F1	3.73± 0.23	6.3± 0.54	320±10
F2	3.78± 0.13	6.4± 0.43	350±5
F3	3.71± 0.011	6.6± 0.57	490± 15
F4	3.80± 0.54	6.5± 0.43	420± 5
F5	3.75± 0.36	6.4± 0.57	450±10
F6	3.69± 0.45	6.4± 0.57	310±10
F7	3.68± 0.98	6.6± 0.23	300± 10
F8	3.76± 0.21	6.3± 0.45	421± 15
F9	3.73± 0.11	6.6± 0.34	480± 5
F10	3.78± 0.78	6.4± 0.23	430± 10

The model fitting graphs for each formulation are shown in graph no.7 to 25.

Table No. 7: Cumulative % Drug release of Formulation F1 to F10.

Time Hrs	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.5	11.59	16.4	9.47	10.66	7.92	11.71	11.01	8.62	13.76	12.87
1	19.67	32.25	16.85	22.86	15.21	16.96	17.73	11.58	18.97	20.14
2	34.36	46.83	31.58	30.91	21.13	31.78	25.25	16.01	24.96	27.49
3	44.85	62.98	45.74	46.15	35.75	41.61	39.46	23.36	41.14	39.21
4	62.68	76.44	54.20	52.30	54.84	66.19	55.27	31.49	57.49	55.32
5	74.89	82.18	64.93	66.33	64.03	76.37	66.83	47.62	66.03	70.88
6	83.59	94.39	74.31	81.91	71.14	86.64	81.44	63.90	81.89	82.30
7	92.37	99.58	85.23	90.53	81.93	92.87	91.78	74.59	88.48	88.10
8	99.78		90.42	97.8	92.09	99.15	98.54	82.50	95.13	96.11
9			95.66	100.17	100.18			95.52	99.67	100.60
10			99.49					100.75		

Table No. 8: Ex-vivo Drug release of Mucoadhesive Buccal patches of Dimenhydrinate (F3) with Porcine Buccal mucosa.

Time inhrs	Log time	SQ.RT of time	Abs (276nm)	Cum% release	Log cum% release
0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.5	-0.301	0.707	0.072	10.37	0.935
1	0.000	1.000	0.098	14.33	1.063
2	0.301	1.414	0.123	18.21	1.204
3	0.477	1.732	0.165	24.62	1.368
4	0.602	2.000	0.213	32.02	1.498
5	0.698	2.236	0.287	43.30	1.677
6	0.778	2.449	0.362	54.94	1.805
7	0.845	2.645	0.458	69.82	1.872
8	0.903	2.828	0.543	83.39	1.916
9	0.954	3.000	0.567	88.42	1.980
10	1	3.162	0.574	91.06	2.003

DRUG RELEASE KINETICS

Table No. 9: Drug release kinetics.

Batch	Zero orderr ² values	First orderr ² values	Higuchir ² values	Korsmeyer-Peppas r ² values	'n' value
F1	0.984	0.721	0.966	0.997	0.793
F2	0.95	0.815	0.989	0.988	0.667
F3	0.971	0.832	0.978	0.995	0.798
F4	0.980	0.868	0.964	0.989	0.766
F5	0.990	0.794	0.944	0.988	0.897
F6	0.972	0.934	0.953	0.987	0.821
F7	0.994	0.826	0.939	0.985	0.822
F8	0.985	0.777	0.889	0.949	0.894
F9	0.980	0.785	0.955	0.973	0.745
F10	0.980	0.872	0.956	0.983	0.752

Table No. 10: Model fitting for formulation F3.

Formulation	Mathematical models				
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi model	Peppas's model	'n' value
F3	0.971	0.832	0.978	0.995	0.798

Table No. 12: Stability studies after 90 days storage of selected formulation (F3) at Room temperature (RT) and 40^oc and 75%RH.

Storage conditions	Days	Bio adhesive strength	In-vitro residence time	Drug content (mgs)	Cum%drug release (10hrs)
Room temperature	30	182	421	3.70	99.41
	60	183	423	3.71	99.02
	90	185	425	3.65	98.67
At 40 ^o c and 75%RH	30	179	417	3.72	99.45
	60	177	420	3.69	99.08
	90	175	418	3.62	98.12

B) SEM photograph of buccal patch with drug**FIG. NO. 1: SEM PHOTOGRAPH OF FORMULATION F5.****SUMMARY**

Dimenhydrinate is a H₁ Antagonist; it is used in the treatment of vomiting caused by motion sickness. As

the conventional doses release the Dimenhydrinate in just few minutes and therefore the therapeutic concentrations are maintained for a short period of

time generating a need for administration of another dose. Therefore an attempt was made to maintain the therapeutic concentration for longer period of time. This was achieved by developing controlled release drug delivery system.

These controlled release Mucoadhesive buccal patches mainly prepared for release of the drug for longer period of time i.e., 10 hours and utilizing the drug to full extent avoiding unnecessary frequency of dosing.

For the formulation of Mucoadhesive buccal patches HPMC E15, HEC, PVA and PVP were used as matrix forming agents. Other excipients used are Propylene glycol as a plasticizer. Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy confirmed the absence of any drug/polymers/excipients interactions.

The Mucoadhesive buccal patches were prepared by solvent casting method using magnetic stirrer. The prepared controlled release Mucoadhesive buccal patches were evaluated for thickness, folding endurance, weight variation, water uptake, bioadhesive strength, drug content uniformity, surface p^H , Mechanical strength, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), In-vitro release study, Invitro residence time, Ex-vivo drug release study, Stability study and Kinetic study.

Formulation F3 showed good Bioadhesive strength and a controlled drug release and also shown good result for all other parameters when compared with all other formulations. Hence formulation F3 is considered to be the optimized formulation. Stability studies were carried out for F3 formulation they had showed good stability when stored at accelerated stability state as per the ICH guideline and the values were within a permissible limits.

It was observed that Formulations F3 retained the drug release up to 24 hrs. All formulations were subjected for four different models viz. Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas model equations and all the formulations best fit in to the Peppas model by giving the values of diffusional exponent (n) in the range of 0.6-0.9 that indicate the formulation had release the drug by diffusion followed by erosion mechanism.

It was revealed that polymer ratios had significant influence on drug release. Thus conclusion can be made that stable dosage form can be developed for Dimenhydrinate for controlled release by buccal patches.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, an attempt has been done to develop a novel mucoadhesive drug delivery system in the form of the buccal patches for the release of Dimenhydrinate in a bidirectional manner, to maintain

constant therapeutic levels of the drug for long time.

Buccal formulations of Dimenhydrinate in the form of mucoadhesive patches were developed to a satisfactory level in term of drug release, bioadhesive strength, content uniformity, percentage water uptake, surface P^H , thickness and mechanical strength.

Although all buccal patches exhibited satisfactory results, best results were obtained with optimized formulation F3 containing HPMC and HEC in 1:3 ratios. In vitro dissolution studies of the optimized formulation showed that the percentage cumulative drug release about the release of Dimenhydrinate from the patches in the present work appeared to occur due to diffusion and erosion mechanism. The release pattern was found to be non-Fickian.

The above study concluded that the possibility of the making of mucoadhesive drug delivery system for Dimenhydrinate which will be more efficacious and acceptable than conventional drug delivery of Dimenhydrinate and also having satisfactory controlled release profile which may provide an increased therapeutic efficacy.

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